

ADVANCED PEDAGOGICAL EXPERIENCES IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF EDUCATION AND THEIR PRACTICAL APPLICATION

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Abstract. *This article provides information about the modern teacher's ability to widely use innovative methods in the educational process and to be able to implement it. its ease of finding solutions has been studied.*

Keywords: *scientific, national and national, knowledge, skills, acquisition of skills, their interpretation, formation of skills, skills and competence, individual, innovative method, technical means, computer, projector or other technical means.*

The main goal of the reforms in the education system under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev is to train competitive personnel and to train specialist personnel who can make a worthy contribution to Uzbekistan joining the ranks of 50 developed countries in 2035. . Therefore, special attention is being paid to improving the quality and efficiency of our national education system by thoroughly studying foreign experiences and using innovative technologies. attention is paid. In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 20, 2023, we focus on supporting education, which is the biggest investment for New Uzbekistan. "Salvation is in education, salvation is in upbringing, salvation is in knowledge. Because all good goals can be achieved thanks to knowledge and education," he said.

In fact, the consistent and continuous reforms in the education system impose a very responsible task on the teacher of the modern science of education. In the teaching of educational sciences, the goal is to intensively develop the intellectual abilities of students by acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities, interpreting them, forming skills, abilities and competence.

When teaching upbringing, it is recommended to pay attention to the following innovative activities: until then, in traditional education, students were taught only to acquire ready-made knowledge. Such a method would quench independent thinking, creative search, initiative in students now came a period of organizing the educational process on the basis of an updated program and modern lessons that meet the standard requirements. In other words, instead of boring lessons, the demand for teachers who approach the organization of classes with responsibility, are professionally knowledgeable, have methodological skills, are responsible, have perfectly mastered modern, interactive pedagogical technology, are able to organize education on the basis of innovation.

As the teacher prepares for a new lesson, he creatively approaches it and achieves his goal only if he turns each lesson into a single product of creativity. To do this, it is difficult for every day uniformity to escape from the lesson and bring one novelty to each lesson, try to find new-new lesson methods, look for them incessantly, create and constantly work on themselves.

One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time, without excessive mental and physical exertion. Between short periods of time, the supply of certain theoretical knowledge to students, the formation of knowledge, skills, competencies and competencies in them from a certain activity, as well as the control of students' activities, the assessment of the level of knowledge, skills, qualifications and competencies acquired by them, requires a higher pedagogical skill from the teacher and a new approach to the educational process.

Above all, through the use of interactive methods, the teacher acquires the opportunity to objectively assess students' collaborative efforts towards a specific educational goal through organization, orientation, management, control and analysis.

The role of the teacher in interactive lessons partially leads to the orientation of students' activities towards the achievement of lesson goals. The peculiarity of these is that they are achieved only through the joint activities of educators and students.

The process of such pedagogical cooperation has its own characteristics, giving them:

- the fact that the student is forced not to be indifferent during the lesson, to think independently, create and seek;
- ensuring the continuity of students' interest in science in the educational process;
- strengthening students' interest in science independently with a creative approach to each issue;
- can continuously organize the collaborative activities of educators and students.

Today, it is natural that the interest and attention to increase the efficiency of education by using innovative pedagogical and information technologies in the educational process is increasing day by day.

Classes using modern technologies are aimed at helping students find the knowledge they are acquiring, independently study and analyze it, and even draw their own conclusions. In this process, the teacher creates the conditions for the development, formation, learning and upbringing of the individual and the team. In such an educational process, the student becomes the main figure, that is, the subject.

Pedagogists have been in the educational system for years

Why do we teach? What do we teach? How do we teach?

In addition to looking for answers to their questions, they also looked for answers to the question of how to teach effectively and efficiently.

This leads scientists and practitioners to the idea that it is possible to try to turn the educational process into a technologization, that is, a technological process that gives a clearly guaranteed result in terms of the production of teaching. The birth of such an idea created a new direction of pedagogical technology in science. Today, the main reason why special attention is paid to the use of pedagogical technologies in the educational process of educational institutions is the following:

First of all, there is a wide range of opportunities to implement personality-developing education in pedagogical technologies. The newly revised Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education" pays special attention to the implementation of developmental education.

Secondly, pedagogical technologies provide an opportunity to widely introduce a systematic activity approach to the educational process.

Thirdly, pedagogical technology encourages the teacher to pre-design the technological chain, starting with the goals of the educational process, and ending with the creation of a diagnostic system and control of this process.

Fourth, pedagogical technology is based on the use of new tools and information methods. The correct implementation of pedagogical technologies in the educational process leads to the teacher acting as the main organizer or consultant in this process. This requires more independence, creativity and willpower from the student.

The use of any pedagogical technology in the educational process depends on who is teaching the student and who is being taught by the teacher based on personal character.

Therefore, the role and importance of modern teaching methods, interactive methods, and innovative technologies in the educational process of educational institutions is incomparable.

Pedagogical technology and the knowledge and experience of their use in education ensure that students acquire knowledge and advanced skills. According to some teachers, researchers and practitioners who are studying the issues and problems of pedagogical technology, pedagogical technology is only related to information technology and technical means of teaching, computer, projector, which must be used in the teaching process. or other technical means. In our opinion, the main basis of pedagogical technology depends on the technologies chosen by the teacher or student to achieve a guaranteed result from the set goal.

A modern teacher should be able to use and implement innovative methods in the process of education.

Factors of using "Three Roots of the Problem" technology in educational science classes. We will analyze the experience of using the "Three Roots of the Problem" technology, which is aimed at the formation of competencies in students, when passing complex topics in educational classes. He tried to make it easier to find a solution by first focusing on the root of complex topics in education classes, then dividing it into conditional three, and then dividing it into three smaller problems by itself. It is known that one of the aspects that make it difficult for the student to learn in education classes is the time when great people lived, the heritage of great ancestors, and it is important to tell the qualities that should be formed on the basis of it. All of them are very difficult to remember. Therefore, each solution of the problem guides the listener to work from simplicity to complexity, but it is necessary to pay attention to the consistency between the solutions of the problems, that they should complement each other and depend on each other. First of all, the listener should be able to think logically and find the three bases above the reality that he considers to be the most important in the given period.

Problem 1: The Great Thinker:

First: The listener studies the activities, achievements, and achievements of a great thinker who wrote works on the science of education.

Second: a great thinker learns information about the events of the time a person lived.

Thirdly: a great thinker learns about a person's followers, students, descendants and successors, and this process will definitely be transferred to his class.

Problem 2: the legacy of a great thinker:

First: To form the ability to use the material and spiritual wealth left by our great ancestors in their lives;

Second: On the basis of studying the educational works handed down to us by our great ancestors, he will enrich his knowledge and use it in the life of students, and opportunities will arise for him to correct and fill in the shortcomings of students.

Third: He understands the events of this period and learns their importance today.

Problem 3: virtues and shortcomings that should be formed in students

First: conditions are created for harmoniously mastering national and national qualities.

Second: The meaning and content of 10 virtues that should be formed in the science of education will be mastered.

Third: Important skills such as the importance of the mentioned qualities today and how they are used in everyday life are inculcated.

Summary. Scientific, methodological, psychological and didactic advantages of the "Three Roots of the Problem" technology:

Using "Three Roots of the Problem" in lessons requires the student to know specific scientific facts. When a particularly complex topic is covered, the student learns the concepts acquired during the lesson step by step, and in the process of learning each assignment, the materials related to the topic are mastered.

In the communicative competence of the students during the lesson, the ability to verbally describe the topic, express their independent opinion and relate it to everyday life, the competence to work with information is formed. Also, the achievements of students, such as the processes of working with materials from the press and the Internet, become a habit.

"The three roots of the problem" can be used at any stage of the lesson, and it can also be used throughout the lesson.

In the process of applying the "three roots of the problem" during the lesson's reinforcement of the learned topic and homework, the student first of all searches for various sources, communicates, thinks, and becomes fluent in oral speech.

The most important thing is that the ability to understand reality and explain it logically, to work with sources and literature is formed. Complex topics are given as homework to prepare students in advance.

The student studies the topic and completes the "Three Roots of the Problem", while working with the events and terms surrounding the main person and historical person in the topic. Most importantly, it works with additional resources in the process of completing the "Three Roots of the Problem". Regular use of the method increases students' activity in class and interest in science. The fact that the method consists of several unique stages and is carried out in the style of a game ensures that the student will not get bored.

The simplicity of the method does not cause difficulties for the teacher during its application, therefore it can be used in small classes.

The use of this technology in the reinforcement phase of the lesson and in repetition lessons is more effective. At the same time, the listener will have the opportunity to work with his student both individually and in a group, and at the end he will test their knowledge.

By announcing the results of the test and explaining the correct answers given, the topic is reinforced.

The purpose of the "Three Roots of the Problem" technology:

- To explain to the students about the past of our ancestors, the events and events of the time when our ancestors lived with a completely impartial and new approach;

- Involvement in certain life issues;
- Development of creativity;
- Development of logical thoughts;
- Combines the knowledge gained during the educational process with practice

The task of the "Three Roots of the Problem" technology:

- Give assignments to students divided into groups;
- Use of computers, information technologies and electronic textbooks;
- Use of visual aids, maps;
- Using different methods and games to evaluate students;
- It is to strengthen immunity against the negative aspects of current globalization in the mind and consciousness of students.

The "three roots of the problem" technology makes it easier to study complex topics in education classes based on problem-based learning, focusing on the root of the problem and finding its solution.

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